

FEATURES OF INFORMATION ANALYSIS AND PLANNING IN THE ACTIVITIES OF PREVENTION INSPECTORS

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Abstract: This article analyzes information analysis and planning in the activities of prevention inspectors, discusses the opinions of legal scholars in this regard, and develops proposals and recommendations by the author.

Keywords: prevention inspectors, information analysis, planning analysis.

The reforms implemented during the years of independence laid the foundation for democratization and liberalization of the judicial sphere, increasing the role and importance of protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens. The role and significance of crime prevention in the country's anti-crime policy have significantly increased. In short, as N. Kuldashev said, ensuring public order and security in every country is defined as a strategic task. Our country has also created a unique system and legal mechanism in this matter.[1] Information and analytical activities in the system of internal affairs bodies are carried out by employees with special and general skills. Information and analytical activities in the system of internal affairs bodies are carried out by employees with special and general skills.

Employees of each specialized service of the internal affairs bodies need to know how to analyze information and thereby systematically plan their future activities. The reason for this is that information and analytical activity is a comprehensive process that is constantly carried out in any society and in various spheres of social life. Therefore, at present, every employee must know the methods and tools of information analysis and forecasting work, as well as be able to effectively use them in researching emerging situations. Ignoring or not being able to use scientific methods can negatively impact not only the waste of time and effort but also the subsequent adoption of important management decisions.

Currently, "A completely new system of crime prevention and anti-crime measures has been created. It has become an urgent task not only to combat the consequences of offenses by threatening with punishment but also to prevent the commission of illegal actions, first of all, to study and analyze the causes of each offense more deeply and develop proposals and plans to eliminate them." [2] Effective organization, management, and coordination of the activities of prevention inspectors of internal affairs bodies is a process related to planning and information exchange.

Therefore, as Sh. Kushbakov said, it is necessary to organize preventive activities as a service assumed by the state by the authorities or other powers and having law enforcement functions, internal organizational unity, and strictly defined powers within the framework of law.[3] The expression of a unified scheme of preventive activities of internal affairs bodies is a necessary condition for its analysis: information analysis and planning activities. According to him, information analysis and planning activities have always been one of the main methods of fulfilling the political, economic, and social tasks of society. The late entry of information analysis and planning activities into the field of legal order strengthening

compared to other areas of public administration can be explained by the fact that the process of eliminating crime is more complex and longer than previously thought. Information analysis and planning of the activities of preventive inspectors play an important role in the types of crime prevention, their role in the system of law enforcement measures and social management, the significance and interrelationship of the components that make up the structure that implements them in forecasting, information provision, planning, legal, organizational-tactical, methodological, and material-technical support of the activities of the preventive service.

The collection and aggregation of information in internal affairs bodies is a priority element of the organizational work of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, aimed at creating the necessary conditions for the performance of official duties assigned to these bodies by current legislation and regulatory documents. Information support for the management activities of internal affairs bodies is one of the priority tasks, and the fulfillment of the tasks assigned to the internal affairs bodies in maintaining public order and combating crime depends on the successful fulfillment of these tasks.

The processes of systematic analysis of practical problems identified by the internal affairs bodies in the field of public order protection, crime prevention, and crime prevention, as well as the effective use of methods and tools of information-analytical and planning activities of the inspector in the analysis of situations, and the forecasting of the criminogenic situation, are directly related to the activity of information analysis. Information and analytical activity in internal affairs bodies is a creative process, as a result of which it becomes a final product that helps to analyze relevant information. A document prepared based on data collected, evaluated, and interpreted through the information and analytical process is its result.

The analytical document, which is the result of information and analytical activity, should be presented in such a way as to clearly and clearly demonstrate its significance in solving a specific task in the activities of internal affairs bodies.

This definition helps to explain the difference between the raw material and the final product of information work. The purpose of the information and analytical activity of the prevention inspector in the process of work is, first and foremost, to develop future work plans for preventive measures based on the correct analysis and direct analysis of the criminogenic situation in the administrative territory, to see the causal conditions with a comprehensive analysis of the causes of the commission of offenses, to systematically analyze areas with a difficult criminogenic situation, to study the committed offenses, the persons who committed them, and to deeply analyze their behavior, to analyze the results of the study of the effectiveness of When organizing information-analytical and planning activities, the prevention inspector must possess special and general skills.

That's why every prevention should be taken today. Ignoring scientific methods, not being able to use them, leads not only to the employee's excessive expenditure of time and energy, but also to the deterioration of the criminogenic situation in the area and the increase in the number of offenses.

In conclusion, it can be said that the collection, analysis, and analysis of information by the internal affairs bodies will open up a wide path for systematic planning of their activities in the future.

Also, by analyzing and planning information, employees of internal affairs bodies achieve the sequence of solving their assigned tasks, uniform provision with personnel, financial, material and technical, and other resources, effective use of forces and resources, and by improving information analysis and planning activities, they achieve the goal of further improving the quality of the activities of internal affairs bodies.

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